

Maturity

Depending on the variety, sorghum matures between 85-100 days

Harvesting

Simple hand sickles or knives are used for harvesting. The crop is ready for harvesting when the black scar appears beneath the seed coat and the grain is hard.

Drying, threshing and winnowing

- Panicle should be well dried before threshing
- Dry on the drying floor or tarpaulin for 3-5 days
- Keep crop away from rain or moist conditions
- Threshed grain is winnowed to remove chuff

Storage and treatment

- ▶ Grain must be well dried before storage
- ▶ Storage can be in cribs or warehouses
- ▶ Bags should be well stacked on wooden pallets above the floor
- ▶ Grain could be stored on panicles but pest control particularly weevils has to be done.
- ▶ Can store grain in hermetic sacks or bags.

IMPROVED SORGHUM VARIETIES IN UGANDA

NAROSORG 1

Superior to SESO 1, Good brewing qualities, 100% free of tannins, White seeded, Suitable for lager beer production, Drought tolerant/stay green, Yields up to 2,800 kg/ha

NAROSORG 2

Red-brown colour, Drought tolerant, Tolerant to Striga weed, Resistant to bird damage due to high tannins, For food and local brew
Easily threshed, Yields 2740Kg/ha.

NAROSORG 3

White seeded, Drought tolerant, Juicy stalk and suitable for forage, Yields 2783 Kg/ha..

NAROSORG 4

Superior to SESO 3, Brown seeded, Tolerant to striga weeds, Resistant to smut disease, Easily threshed, Yields 2544 Kg/ha.

SESO 1

White seeded, Yields 1800-2200kg/ha, Early Maturing

SESO 3

Brown seeded, Yields 1850-2300 Kg/ha , early maturing, (80 days)

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Sorghum Production Guide

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Introduction

Sorghum is the third most important staple cereal food crop in Uganda after maize and millet.

RECOMMENDED SORGHUM PRODUCTION PRACTICES

Seedbed

Prepare a fine seedbed early before the on-set of rains

Seed Rate

Plant 5kg of seed per acre or 15 Kg of seed per hectare.

Planting Time

Planting should be done at the onset of rains, usually;

- ▶ March-April for first rains
- ▶ August-September for second rains

Method of planting

Most farmers broadcast but row planting is recommended for the following reasons;

Easy field operations like weeding, bird scaring and harvesting Ox-drawn implements can be used in field operations like weeding Optimum plant population for optimum yields and higher income can be obtained.

Spacing

Ranges from 60 X 20cm in wet areas to 90 X 90cm in dry areas
Tall varieties require wide spacing

Thinning

Thin at 3-4 weeks after emergence depending on seedling growth rate to 2 plants per hole.
Thinning should be done when there is adequate moisture to avoid stress.

Gap Filling

Gap fill by transplanting within 2 weeks after emergence under wet soils.

Weeding

Weed twice in a growing season for better crop establishment.

Pest and Disease Management

Major pests include;
Stem borers
Shoot flies
Sorghum midge
Birds

Pest Control and Management

Cultural: Early planting, Remove and destroy crop debris, crop rotation, grow resistant varieties.

▶ Chemical:

Endosulfan, Ambush, Marshal, as sprays. Granulated forms of Ambush, Bulldock, Dipterex applied in plant whorls 4 weeks after crop emergence to control stem borers. Use recommended rate according to manufacturers instructions.

Common Sorghum Diseases

- ▶ Smuts (foliar and head)
- ▶ Rust (foliar)
- ▶ Ergot (head)
- ▶ Anthracnose (foliar and head)

